

SANSA NEWSLETTER

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IN MEMORY OF DR PETRA SIERWALD

We in South Africa were sorry to learn that Dr Petra Sierwald passed away in May 2026. Petra was a highly respected scientist who dedicated her career to studying spiders and millipedes and advancing global knowledge about biodiversity. She led the development of the first global millipede species database (MilliBase.org) and served as its Chief Taxonomic Editor. She also obtained decades of federal grants for projects including the Spider Tree-of-Life and served as editor for several scientific journals. She supported conservation by improving scientific data and classification systems and Influenced both research and education in zoology.

Petra Sierwald was also an international scientist and her research spanned the globe, from Mexico and Panama to Myanmar, Vietnam, and South Africa. Here we, the South Africans especially want to pay tribute to Petra for her contribution toward spider research Africa. We were very fortunate that she spent some time in South Africa when she was stationed at the Natal Museum. During her stay here she undertook extensive field work and she made valuable contributions towards resolving genera of several African Pisauridae. But it is especially her work on *Nilus* (then *Thalassius*) that was invaluable.

She also played an important role in placing South Africa on the map in regard with arachnid research. In 1996 she attended the 5th African Arachnological Colloquium organized by the African Arachnological Society (AFRAS) at Klein Kariba (see photographs). She enjoyed this meeting in the African bush so much that on returning to the USA she contacted Dr Norman Platnick, the then president, of the International Society of Arachnida (ISA) suggesting that the South Africans organize the next International Congress of the Arachnida.

This resulted in the 15th International Congress of the Arachnida being hosted at Badplaas in 2001. It was done in true African style with Swazi dancers and Marimba players. This in strong contrast with the very classy congress she had previously organized in Chicago.

So we in South Africa are grateful that we were part of Petra's life for a short while—for that we are grateful!

Delegates at the 5th African Arachnological Colloquium

Some delegates giving the AFRAS salute

Delegates ready for a day of spider and scorpion hunting hoping to win the "catch-of-the-day" prize.

Rudy Jocqué telling them about his AFRAS dream

Petra, Peter Jäger and Ansie and a Swazi dancer at the congress dinner

NEW PUBLICATION

YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T., SIMBA V. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2026. A checklist of ground-dwelling spiders in a banana orchard in Hazyview in Mpumalanga province. *Koedoe* 68(1), a1883. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v68i1.1883>

ABSTRACT: Banana orchards like other crops are attacked by insect pests. Although spiders are among the natural enemies of these pests, we have no records of the different types of spider species that occur in the banana orchards. As such, in this study we determined the occurrence of species of ground-dwelling spiders in a banana orchard. In addition, we compared species richness, abundance and composition of spiders sampled using pitfall traps in the colder (July) and warmer (November) months. A total of 635 specimens from 14 families, 30 genera and 33 species were recorded. Although the Corinnidae was represented by two species only, one of these species, *Copa flavoplumosa* Simon, 1886, contributed 53% of the total abundance of spiders recorded from the banana orchard. The Lycosidae, Salticidae, Gnaphosidae and Zodariidae were the most species-rich families, while the rest of the families were represented by one/two species. There was greater species richness and abundance of spiders sampled in November than July. In addition, our study showed that assemblages of ground-dwelling spiders are influenced by season. Although most of the collected spider species are represented by fewer individuals, their presence suggests a greater importance of spiders in the biological control of insect pests. Furthermore, despite the low numbers of individuals and species of spiders that we collected during the colder month, variation in species composition between the warmer and colder months suggests continuous presence of spiders in the banana orchard, which augurs well for pest control.

Copa flavoplumosa Simon, 1886, contributed 53% of the total abundance of spiders recorded from the banana orchard. Credit: Charles Haddad.

NEW PHOTO GUIDE

WOOLSEY E. 2026. Ventral differentiation of South African *Leucauge* species – Summary Visual Field Guide 2026: 1–5.

ABSTRACT: *Leucauge* White, 1841, is represented in South Africa by nine species. Six of these are commonly encountered in the region as reflected by observations published on iNaturalist. The descriptions for these species are well established in literature. However, when working from photographs, we are often presented with only the ventral view. The large volume of sightings reported on iNaturalist offers an opportunity to refine visual identification by comparing numerous individual findings and looking for recurring patterns that may differentiate species. This guide focuses on the ventral differences. The recurrent patterns for each species are summarized using schematics and a dichotomous key was produced that includes three groups. Each group is illustrated by photographs and annotated schematics.

Ventral Differentiation of South African *Leucauge* Species – Quick Reference Schematics

Leucauge decorata ventral view

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HU C.H. 2026. *Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925 is the valid name for the genus *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945 (Araneae, Theridiidae, Hadrotarsinae). *The Indochina Entomologist* 2(22): 227–230. doi: [10.70590/ice.2026.02.22](https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2026.02.22)

ABSTRACT: *Euryopsis* Menge, 1868 is the second most diverse genus of the subfamily Hadrotarsinae Thorell, 1881 (Hu et al. 2026; World Spider Catalog 2026). Levi (1954) and Levi & Levi (1962) revised this genus and proposed several synonyms, including *Acanthomysmena* Mello-Leitão, 1944, *Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925, *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945, *Mufila* Bryant, 1949, among others. Yoshida (2002) revalidated *Emertonella* and noted that “all the species of the *Eu. emertoni* group designed by Levi (1954) belong to this genus”, but did not formally transfer the species. Hu et al. (2026) formally transferred all species of the *Eu. emertoni* group, together with 16 additional species, to *Emertonella*, including *Em. scriptipes* (Banks, 1908), the type species of *Dipoenoides*. However, because *Dipoenoides* has priority over *Emertonella*, the use of the latter generic name by Hu et al. (2026) renders it invalid under the Principle of Priority (ICZN 1999: Art. 23). The aims of the current paper are to revalidate *Dipoenoides* and to transfer 35 species currently placed in *Emertonella* to *Dipoenoides*.

In the World Spider Catalog (2026) two species *Dipoenoides episinoides* and *D. funebris* are listed from South Africa.

Dipoenoides episinoides (Peter Webb)

Dipoenoides funebris (Peter Webb)

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S, LYLE R., RAIMONDO D.C., SETHUSA T., FOORD S., HADDAD C., LOTZ L., HENDRICKS S.E., MONYEKI M.S. & VAN DER COLFF D. 2026. Spiders. National Biodiversity Assessment 2025. South African National Biodiversity Institute. <http://nba.sanbi.org.za/>

In South Africa, from 2016 to 2019, a total of 2 265 species from 76 069 records were used for the first time in a conservation assessment. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species Categories and Criteria, which reflect a species’ extinction risk, were used. This information form part of the National Biodiversity Assessment 2025.

Species richness map based on kernel density plots of a) endemic species and b) rare and threatened spider species in South Africa.

The NBA 2025 document was released in February 2026 and the document is available on the SANBI website.

Note: For a checklist of the threatened spider species in South Africa see pp. 10–16.

NEW PHOTO GUIDE

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L. N. & UYS W. 2026. *The Salticidae of South Africa. Part 4 (K-Mogrus)*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 70 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20542599>

In part 4 the following genera and species are discussed:

- *Kima* Peckham & Peckham, 1902 (3 spp.)
- *Langelurillus* Próchniewicz, 1994 (5 spp.)
- *Langona* Simon, 1901 (7 spp.)
- *Leptochestes* Thorell, 1870 (new)
- *Manzumia* Azarkina, 2020 (2 spp.)
- *Massagris* Simon, 1900 (6 spp.)
- *Meleon* Wanless, 1984 (1 sp.)
- *Menemrus* Simon, 1868 (16 spp.) Quick photo key
- *Mexcala* Peckham & Peckham, 1902 (4 spp.)
- *Microbianor* Logunov, 2000 (3 spp.)
- *Modunda* Simon, 1901 (1 sp.)
- *Mogrus* Simon, 1882 (2 spp.)

In Part 4, the maps were compiled by Dr. Wynand Uys and include distribution data from the SANSa database as well as research grade locations downloaded from iNaturalist. This provided important additional data for each species.

NEW FAMILY FOR SOUTH AFRICA

LI Z.Y., ZHANG C. & ZHANG F. 2026. Advancing the systematics of Araneae: ultraconserved elements phylogenomics demonstrates the non-monophyly of Miturgidae Simon, 1886 and supports the familial rank of Systariidae Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001. *Insect Systematics and Diversity* 10(3, ixag022): 1–13. doi: [10.1093/isd/ixag022](https://doi.org/10.1093/isd/ixag022)

ABSTRACT: The systematic status of the family Miturgidae Simon, 1886 and related subfamilies has long been problematic, primarily due to challenges in interpreting morphological characters and limited molecular sampling. In this study, we reconstruct the phylogeny of Miturgidae using ultraconserved elements and estimate its divergence time. Our results suggest that Systariinae does not belong to Miturgidae, but rather is sister to all other families of the Dionychoa B clade. Consequently, we elevate it to family rank as Systariidae Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001 and discuss its morphological synapomorphies. Furthermore, our analyses place Miturgidae as the sister clade to Viridasiidae + Selenopidae under multiple phylogenetic methods. Divergence time estimates indicate an ancient origin of Systariidae in the Early Cretaceous (ca. 112 Ma), while Miturgidae appeared later during the Late Cretaceous (ca. 76 Ma). This study significantly advances the understanding of the phylogeny, systematics, and evolutionary history of Miturgidae and Systariidae, providing a robust foundation for future taxonomic and evolutionary research.

SYSTARIIDAE NEW FAMILY FOR SOUTH AFRICA

The genus *Coryssiphus* Simon, 1903 represented by two South African species: *C. cinerascens* Simon, 1903 and *C. praeustus* Simon, 1903 both known only from areas around Cape Town, South Africa. It was originally described in the Clubionidae (Liocraniinae). With the revision of *Coryssiphus* by Bosselaers (2024) the genus was transferred to Miturgidae (Systariinae). But now Li *et al.* (2026) elevate Systariinae to family rank as Systariidae Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001.

Credit: Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R., VAN DER MESCHT A., BOOYSEN R., CHRISTIAAN R., STANDER A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN AARD A.C. & FOORD S.H. 2026. One time only: determining spider diversity along a latitudinal gradient in South Africa's arid Succulent Karoo and Desert biomes using a rapid sampling protocol. *Acta Oecologica* 132 (2026) 104186.

ABSTRACT: The Succulent Karoo Biome (SKB) is distributed in the western and southern parts of South Africa and is an entirely arid global biodiversity hotspot, but it is severely undersampled for spiders. To address this gap, we used a standardized sampling protocol to collect arachnids from four biotopes (open plain, riparian vegetation, east- and west-facing mountain slopes) using three methods along a latitudinal gradient of five adjacent degree-squares in South Africa's arid western interior to determine how latitude, biotopes, sampling methods and climate affect spider assemblages and diversity. A total of 6497 spiders were collected, representing 305 species and 39 families. Beating yielded the most individuals but the fewest species ($n = 3710$, $S = 130$), hand collecting in litter the most species and intermediate numbers ($n = 1646$, $S = 213$) and hand collecting from rocks collected the lowest numbers and intermediate species richness ($n = 1141$, $S = 150$). Abundance and species richness showed a general bell-shaped pattern along the transect, peaking at Akkerendam Nature Reserve ($n = 1839$, $S = 129$). Hand collecting from leaf litter was the most important contributor to spider species richness, with a lower species accumulation rate than beating or hand collecting from rocks. Spider composition from rocks and leaf litter showed some overlap, whereas beating sampled a highly distinct fauna across sites. In total, 519 specimens were sequenced (cytochrome c oxidase subunit I, COI), and this data is publicly available on the SPIZA project on the Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD).

Some of the areas sampled

Paradonea variegata Credit: Ruan Booysen

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S, MUNYAI T.C, BIRD T.L. & FOORD S.H.† 2026. The faunistic diversity of the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Waterberg District in the Limpopo Province of South Africa. *African Invertebrates* (in press).

ABSTRACT: The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) conducted surveys in the Waterberg District of the Limpopo Province, South Africa, over more than 40 years. The first annotated checklist for the Waterberg District is provided here, along with the global distributions, endemism, and conservation assessments for each species, as per the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) criteria. A total of 54 families, 292 genera, and 600 species were recorded. The study highlights species of special conservation concern, as well as the nine species endemic to the Waterberg District. Salticidae (95 species), followed by Thomisidae (80 species), Araneidae (53 species), and Gnaphosidae (48 species), are the most species-rich families. In contrast, single species represent 14 families. Most species (546; 91.2%) are widely distributed, with no known threats, and are classified as being of Least Concern, whereas 34 species (5.6%) are still listed as Data Deficient. Seven species (1.2%) are of special concern, and 11 species were not evaluated due to unresolved taxonomy. The Waterberg District has a rich spider fauna, accounting for 66.3% of the known spider fauna of the Limpopo Province, 25.6% of the total spider fauna of South Africa, and had nine species endemic to the District.

Some of the 600 species sampled from the Waterberg District in the Limpopo province

SOME INTERESTING FIELD OBSERVATIONS

A CRAB SPIDER *STIPROPELLA* AND ANTS

SANSA have received very interesting photographs on the crab spider *Stipropella* interactions with some ants. The spider is a thomisid and it belongs to the genus *Stiphropella*. This genus is monotypic and only the female of the species *S. gracilis* Lawrence, 1952 was described from Weenen Nature Reserve in KZN. It is one of the few crab spiders that are found on the soil surface. Only a few crab spider genera are associated with ants. Some species mimic ants (*Amyciaea*) and some prey on them, e.g. *Sylligma* and *Simorcus* species.

Philipp Hoenle wrote: The spider was not trying to eat the *Anoplolepis steingroeveri* ants, and there was no aggression from the *Anoplolepis* even directly next to the nest. The spider grabbed a leg, but eventually let go of the ant after a couple of minutes I did take a video of the interaction and have some more notes. It was repeatedly using its front legs to touch the ants body, which is a typical myrmecophile behavior to gain the smell of their host ants (cuticular hydrocarbons), reducing the aggression. This is particularly impressive as *Anoplolepis* are quite aggressive towards everything. There might be even more going on, perhaps its a brood predator or uses ant nests as protection for younger stages.

Also have a look at **Spider defense force**
 Do ants know how to handle spider webs? Philipp Hoenle
<https://myrmecophili.substock.com/p/spider-defense-force>

Series of photographs taken by Frans over a two-day period

Frans Pretorius sent us the following images and wrote: " I shot some photo's of interesting interaction between ants and a spiders. Four spiders, appearing to be in the family Thomisidae, were found between a group of *Anoplolepis custodiens* ants. There was no attacking or fighting or predation taking place. The ants were dragging the spiders into holes and crevices as if they were "protecting" them." Frans went back the next day and the spiders were still there very "happy" between the ants. Unfortunately, after collecting them they were killed at his house by house ants! *Anoplolepis custodiens* are aggressive, fast-moving ants and when they sense anything that can be perceived as a threat workers will swarm and attack. The only known interaction of them with other animals are with honeydew-producing insect pests, as honeydew forms part of their diet. *Anoplolepis custodiens* tending of honeydew-producing pest species can lead to these ants causing problems in some agricultural settings.

SOME INTERESTING FIELD OBSERVATIONS

THOMISUS SPECIES AS POSSIBLE "POLLINATORS"?

There is no published evidence that *Thomisus* species act as true pollinators, but they regularly contact reproductive structures, carry pollen incidentally, and may *occasionally* contribute to pollen transfer as a by-product of ambush hunting on flowers. Current literature treats them as predators on flowers, not pollinators.

Thomisus species are among the most likely to show incidental pollen transfer because they:

- Sit directly on flowers
- Are in contact with anthers or stigma
- Remain on flowers for long periods
- Move between flowers
- Have hairy bodies that can trap pollen
- Possibly collect pollen loads on palpi, chelicerae, legs or abdomen

Credit: Vida van der Walt

There is also no evidence that spiders feed on pollen. But images of crab spiders often show them covered in pollen. Because spiders clean themselves multiple times a day using their legs and mouthparts to remove dust, pollen, silk, parasites, and debris from their bodies — especially from their eyes, sensory hairs, and spinnerets they may possibly digest some.

Credit: Angus Burns

Credit: Munton Jackson

MORE ON *PROPOSTIRA* Simon, 1894 IN SOUTH AFRICA

In the Theridiidae SANSA Photo Identification Guide 2021, the genus *Propostira* Simon, 1894 was listed only as preliminarily possible in South Africa. It is a genus recognised by the flat, elongated bright orange-yellow or brown-red carapace and the abdomen with four humps. The legs are long, the first pair longest with long trochanters, the femur and tibia are robust, and the metatarsus and tarsus are thin. Only the females are known from two species. We still need to confirm the species from South Africa.

Currently, on the iNaturalist platform and in the SANSA database, 10 records of *Propostira* are known. They were mainly recorded in Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and KwaZulu-Natal, with one record from the Garden Route. Little is known about their behaviour, but a recent article described the very interesting way they trap their prey on leaves. The spider has been nicknamed the "ballista" for the speed and force with which it flings prey into its web.

Female *Propostira* sp. from Mpumalanga.

Credit: Hannes Claassens

Spider which uses spring trap to capture prey discovered in Australia <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c70y138y995o>

NEW PUBLICATIONS ON SOUTH AFRICAN ARACHNIDS

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. & WEBB P. 2026. Notes on *Leptopholcus gracilis* Berland, 1920 a leaf-dwelling spider from South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 23–25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19234869>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. 2026. The first record of *Cyrtarachne finniganae* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 22. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19235925>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. 2026. Present status of *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) in South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 26–27. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19235173>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. 2026. Quick guide to the grass long bodied orb-web spiders (Araneae: Araneidae) in South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 53–43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19235621>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. 2026. A review of the Araneidae genera and species in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 9–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19235407>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN DER WALT V., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & UYS W. 2026. *The Salticidae of South Africa*. Part 4 (K-Mogrus). Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, 70 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20542599>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LYLE R., RAIMONDO D.C., SETHUSA T., FOORD S., HADDAD C., LOTZ L., HENDRICKS S.E., MONYEKI M.S. & VAN DER COLFF D. 2026. Spiders. National Biodiversity Assessment 2025. South African National Biodiversity Institute. <http://nba.sanbi.org.za/>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., MUNYAI T.C., BIRD T.L. & FOORD S.H.† 2026. The faunistic diversity of the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the Waterberg District in the Limpopo Province of South Africa. *African Invertebrates* (in press).

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A. & VAN DEN BERG A. 2026. Spider diversity of the Springbok Flats in the Limpopo Province of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 28–43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19235692>

HADDAD C.R., VAN DER MESCHT A., BOOYSEN R., CHRISTIAAN R., STANDER A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN AARD A.C. & FOORD S.H. 2026. One time only: determining spider diversity along a latitudinal gradient in South Africa's arid Succulent Karoo and Desert biomes using a rapid sampling protocol. *Acta Oecologica* 132 (2026) 104186.

HU C.H. 2026. *Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925 is the valid name for the genus *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945 (Araneae, Theridiidae, Hadrotarsinae). *The Indochina Entomologist* 2(22): 227–230. [doi: 10.70590/ice.2026.02.22](https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2026.02.22)

KGATLA M.M., BARKER C., BAXTER J.R., BESTER-VAN DER MERWE A.E., CHAISI M., CHAKONA A, et al. (2026) An overview of DNA barcoding of biodiversity in South Africa. *PLoS One* 21(4): e0345173. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0345173>

LI ZY., ZHANG C. & ZHANG F. 2026. Advancing the systematics of Araneae: ultraconserved elements phylogenomics demonstrates the non-monophyly of Miturgidae Simon, 1886 and supports the familial rank of Systariidae Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001. *Insect Systematics and Diversity* 10: 1–13. [doi: 10.1093/isd/ixag022](https://doi.org/10.1093/isd/ixag022)

LOTZ L. 2026. Key to the Harvestmen genera (Opiliones) of South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 57: 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19236026>

SPEAR D., BROWN K., LIDDLE N., PARENZEE C.J. & VAN WILGEN N.J., 2026. Optimising species checklists for protected areas in the digital age. *Koedoe* 68(1), a1858. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v68i1.1858>

YEKWAYO I., MWABVU T., SIMBA V. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2026. A checklist of ground-dwelling spiders in a banana orchard in Hazyview in Mpumalanga province. *Koedoe* 68(1), a1883. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v68i1.1883>

NOTE: Prof Charles Haddad was asked to present one of the Keynotes.

For the first circular of the colloquium see pp. 38–39 or contact Dr. Tharina Bird.

A checklist of the threatened spider species in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Charles Haddad², Leon Lotz³, Robin Lyle⁴ & Stefan Foord^{†1}

¹ University of Venda; ² University of the Free State; ³ National Museum, Bloemfontein; ⁴ Agricultural Research Council

ABSTRACT: The emerging field of conservation biogeography examines species' distribution dynamics and their relationship to biodiversity conservation. In South Africa, from 2016 to 2019, a total of 2 265 species from 76 069 records were used for the first time in a conservation assessment. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species Categories and Criteria, which reflect a species' extinction risk, were used. Only South African species were assessed; Eswatini and Lesotho were excluded. Of the assessed taxa, most species (1 445, 63%) are widely distributed and have no known threats, while 691 species (31%) have insufficient information to make a direct or indirect assessment. Only 60 species (2.6%) were assessed as IUCN Threatened Species: four species (0.1%) are classified as Critically Endangered (CR), 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN), and 33 species (1.4%) as Vulnerable (VU). The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) uses additional categories for South African taxa to highlight species that they are not necessarily threatened but are of high conservation concern due to extreme rarity and 69 species (3%) were listed as such.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, red listing, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The emerging field of conservation biogeography concerns species' distribution dynamics and their relationship to biodiversity conservation (Robertson *et al.*, 2010). The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), initiated in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), has the primary aim of documenting the arachnid fauna of South Africa. Distribution records for all known South African species were extracted from original descriptions, redescriptions, and revisionary work, as well as from species newly recorded during ecological surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). This resulted in a complete data set as it also included species housed in overseas museum collections. As part of SANSA, all this data was collated in a relational database maintained by the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Descriptions of South African spider species experienced two periods of rapid growth, the first at the start of the previous century and the second, which corresponds with the initiation of SANSA in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). SANSA has resulted in a 33% increase in newly recorded and described spider species. The number of accessions in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection (Figs 1 & 2) increased by 350% since the initiation of SANSA phase II in 2006, when funding became available from the Threatened Species Program at the South African Biodiversity Institute (SANBI).

In South Africa from 2016 to 2019, spiders were assessed for the first time using the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species Categories and Criteria, which reflect a species' extinction risk. In the latest checklist 2 265 species are listed from South Africa with their conservation assessment (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Of the assessed taxa, only 78 species (4%) were assessed as threatened and a checklist of these species of special concern is provided here.

METHODS

The spider species assessed for the first time using the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species categories and criteria only dealt with South African species, Eswatini and Lesotho species were excluded (Foord *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Records in the SANSA database that were not identified up to species level were excluded from the data used for Red List assessments. A total of 23 827 records were therefore used and the distribution of occurrence of species across South Africa was visualised using quarter-degree, degree-square, and density-kernel plots for all records (76 069).

Analysis for Red List assessments was performed using the red data set (Cardoso, 2017). Spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range was used. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO (Foord *et al.*, 2020). EOOs smaller than the AOO were made equal. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualised using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within three categories: data deficient, least concern, and of special concern

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Figures 1-2. 1. The National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection at Roodeplaat. 2. The National Arachnida collection.

IUCN RED LIST CATEGORIES AND CRITERIA

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) uses a standardized system called the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria to classify species according to their risk of extinction. This system was used to do conservation assessments of South African spiders (Table 2). There are nine official categories used in IUCN conservation assessments:

1. **Not Evaluated (NE):** Species that have not yet been assessed against the IUCN criteria.
2. **Data Deficient (DD):** There is inadequate information to make a direct or indirect assessment of extinction risk.
3. **Least Concern (LC):** Species are widespread and abundant; they do not meet the criteria for a threatened category.
4. **Near Threatened (NT):** Species are close to qualifying for a threatened category or likely to qualify soon.
5. **Vulnerable (VU):** Species face a high risk of extinction in the wild.
6. **Endangered (EN):** Species face a very high risk of extinction in the wild.
7. **Critically Endangered (CR):** Species face an extremely high risk of extinction in the wild.
8. **Extinct in the Wild (EW):** Species survive only in captivity, cultivation, or as a naturalized population outside its historical range.
9. **Extinct (EX):** No reasonable doubt exist that the last individual of the species has died.

SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL BIODIVERSITY INSTITUTE CATEGORIES

The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) use The categories Rare (R) and Critically Rare (CR) although they do not form part of the IUCN system (Table 3). These categories are used to flag species of exceptionally high conservation concern, even when they are not yet declining. They explicitly used it to ensure that naturally range-restricted endemic species are not overlooked in land-use planning, EIAs, or development decisions.

Rare: A species may be listed as Rare if it meets any one of the following:

Restricted range: Extent of Occurrence (EOO) < 500 km²

Habitat specialist: Area of Occupancy (AOO) < 20 km²

Low population density: Occurs as single individuals or small subpopulations (often < 50 mature individuals per subpopulation)

Small global population: Fewer than 10 000 mature individuals worldwide

Critically Rare: A species that is extremely range-restricted or confined to a single site, with very few known populations, and where any additional disturbance could immediately drive it towards extinction, even if there is no current decline. This category is used mainly for plants and some invertebrates. In spider and invertebrate assessments, Critically Rare is often applied when: a species is known from one cave, forest patch, mountain slope, or dune system; there may, as yet, be no evidence of decline, but any habitat loss would be catastrophic.

SOUTH AFRICAN SPIDER SPECIES LISTED AT THE IUCN

South Africa has one of the most comprehensive spider conservation assessments in the world and many species have IUCN-style conservation statuses. Only a small number are currently listed individually on the global IUCN website. The IUCN Red List system classifies how endangered a species is using different categories.

RESULTS

Family diversity: In a checklist published by Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2023), 2 265 spider species and subspecies, 495 genera and 71 families were listed. Of the 71 spider families known from South Africa, the Salticidae (jumping spiders) is the most species rich (354 species), followed by the Gnaphosidae (195 species) and Thomisidae (143 species).

Endemicity: Most species (1 419 species, 63%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern. There are 675 spider species (30%) classified as Data Deficient, underscoring the need for further research to better understand them and assess their threat status. Data-deficient species are usually known from only one sex or based on old material without detailed locality data, or where the species are not recently redescribed or illustrated. Many species recorded from South Africa (946 species, 41.4%) are still only known from one sex and 23 species were described from juveniles, resulting in the high number of Data Deficient species.

Species of special concern: Only 60 species (2.6%) were assessed as threatened IUCN species: four species (0.1%) are classified as Critically Endangered (CR), 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN), 33 species (1.4%) are Vulnerable (VU) and 4 species (0.2%) are Near Threatened (NT). The SANBI category flagged 62 species of high conservation concern due to extreme rarity. No spider species is extinct or possibly extinct.

However, it is the smaller, more delicate spiders frequently found in darker, hidden habitats, such as caves, that are of greatest concern. This includes families such as Archaeidae (6 species), Pholcidae (20 species) and some Zodariidae (9 species).

Several of the larger Mygalomorphae ground dwellers are also of special concern but that is mainly because they are not easily seen or collected. This group include: Entypesidae (1 species), Idiopidae (5 species), Microstigmatidae (1 species), Migidae (5 species), Pycnothelidae (1 species), Stasimopidae (4) and Theraphosidae (3) (Table 1 & 2).

TO SUMMARIZE

Threatened species (IUCN) (60 spp.):

- 4 species Critically Endangered (CR)
- 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN)
- 33 species 1.4% as Vulnerable (VU)
- 4 species (0.2%) as Near Threatened (NT)

Rarity categories (SANBI) (62 spp.):

- 17 species (0.8%) were listed as Critically Rare
- 45 species (1.9%) as Rare

More information:

- 1 445 species (63%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern
- 691 species (31%) are data deficient
- Endemism is high, and 1303 species (59%) are only found in South Africa, 2.4% of the World’s fauna
- 946 species, 41.4%) are known only from one sex
- 23 species were described from juveniles

Main threats to spiders: Biodiversity inventories are essential to identify key areas for conservation and to monitor the effects of threats. Research on spider ecology in South Africa focused on local-scale studies on how spider assemblage responses to habitat complexity, landscape scale variables, ecosystem rehabilitation and plant invasions, and disturbance effects such as fire, grazing and chemical control. Spiders face a variety of natural and human-related threats, of which the main threats are:

• PREDATORS

Spiders are a normal part of the food chain and help to keep prey populations balanced in controlling pests in agro-ecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). But many animals hunt spiders for food. This includes animals, such as birds (Kopij, 2000; Jones, 2011), small mammals (Kerley, 1989), monkeys (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2011); reptiles and amphibians such as lizards, frogs and toads (Nagy *et al.*, 1984); insects like wasps and assassin bugs (Gess & Gess, 1980; Nel *et al.*, 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025).

• NATURAL THREATS

Natural disasters such as floods, fires, droughts, and storms can destroy spider habitats, kill spiders, and reduce their food supply, forcing them to move or causing populations to decline. Floods, for example, can destroy burrows and webs, while fires can burn vegetation and directly kill spiders. Studies in South Africa looked at the effect of fire on spiders (Lubin & Crouch, 2003; Uys *et al.*, 2006; Pryke & Samways, 2012; Haddad *et al.*, 2015).

• ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES

Changes in temperature, humidity, or seasons can affect their survival. Extreme weather events can destroy webs and habitats. Currently climate change is making these effects worse, and some studies focus on determining the possible effects (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016).

• HUMAN-RELATED THREATS

Habitat loss is one of the biggest threats. This includes removing places where spiders live and hunt such as deforestation; urban development and farming expansion. Studies examined overgrazing of cattle (Seymour & Dean, 1999; Jansen *et al.*, 2013), sheep farming (Henschel & Lubin, 2018) as well elephant-induced habitat changes (Haddad *et al.*, 2010); effect of long-term mammal herbivory (Ukwevho *et al.*, 2023); effect of Bt-cotton cultivation (Mellet *et al.*, 2006); land use changes (Foord *et al.*, 2018; Joseph *et al.*, 2017; Yekwayo *et al.*, 2017) and mining in coastal dune forest (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wassenaar, 2002, 2006).

• PESTICIDES AND POLLUTION

Chemicals like heavy metals or microplastics affect the ability to produce effective webs. They also reduce reproduction and may reduce spider diversity and abundance and feeding behaviour (Virbhan, 2025). Pesticides and herbicides are among the most detrimental pollutants affecting spider populations in agriculture. Insecticides not only reduce prey availability but also have direct toxic effects on spiders. Research looked at the effect of cover spraying in the control of termites on spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978) and the control of pest species in cotton (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1990). Soil pollution, primarily caused by agricultural runoff, industrial waste, urbanization and heavy metal accumulation, can affect burrowing and ground-dwelling spiders, while semi-aquatic spiders are particularly vulnerable to freshwater and seashore contamination, which can lead to bioaccumulation of toxins.

Artificial light at night significantly affects nocturnal spiders by disrupting their natural behaviours. Many spider species rely on darkness for hunting, mating, and web construction. Increased exposure to artificial lighting can alter circadian rhythms, reduce predation efficiency, and influence web placement.

• INVASIVE SPECIES

Non-native animals or plants can disrupt ecosystems where spiders live. Research in South Africa looked at the effect of invasive weeds such as *Chromolaena odorata* (Mgobozi *et al.*, 2008) and *Opuntia stricta* (Robertson *et al.*, 2011) on spider populations.

TABLE 1. The spider families with the number of species that are currently regard as being of special concern.

FAMILY	SPP.	FAMILY	SPP.
Anapidae	1	Penestomidae	2
Araneidae	3	Pholcidae	20
Archaeidae	6	Phyxelididae	4
Atypidae	2	Pycnothelidae	1
Caponiidae	2	Salticidae	11
Cheiracanthiidae	1	Scytodidae	2
Corinnidae	5	Selenopidae	1
Cyatholipidae	4	Sicariidae	1
Drymusidae	4	Sparassidae	3
Entypesidae	1	Stasimopidae	4
Gallieniellidae	3	Telemidae	1
Hersiliidae	1	Tetragnathidae	1
Idiopidae	5	Theraphosidae	3
Linyphiidae	2	Thomisidae	3
Lycosidae	1	Trachelidae	4
Macrobunidae	2	Zodariidae	9
Microstigmatidae	1	Zoropsidae	3
Migidae	5		

Amaurobioides africana a semi-aquatic spider that is vulnerable for seashore contamination. Credit: Charles Haddad.

TABLE 2. South African spider species off special concern based in the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria.

CRITICALLY ENDANGERED (CR)

Afrarchaea fernkloofensis Lotz, 1996
Afrarchaea entabeniensis Lotz, 2003
Caerostris tinamaze Gregorič, 2015
Diploglena proxila Haddad, 2015

ENDANGERED (EN)

Afrarchaea woodae Lotz, 2006
Cladomelea akermani Hewitt, 1923
Cladomelea debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004
Diploglena dippenaarae Haddad, 2015
Drassodella tenebrosa Lawrence, 1938
Galeosoma hirsutum Hewitt, 1916
Galeosoma pallidum Hewitt, 1915
Galeosoma scutatatum Purcell, 1903
Griswoldia zuluensis (Lawrence, 1938)
Heliophanus africanus Wesolowska, 1986
Homalattus punctatus Peckham & Peckham, 1903
Icius nigricaudus Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009
Moggridgea loistata Griswold, 1987
Moggridgea quercina Simon, 1903
Palystes kreutzmanni Jäger & Kunz, 2010
Procydrela procursor Jocqué, 1999
Quamtana knysna Huber, 2003
Rotundrela rotunda Jocqué, 1999
Smeringopus dehoop Huber, 2012
Stasimopus filmeri Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Stasimopus griswoldi Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Thyenula clarisognata Wesolowska et al., 2014
Thyenula rufa Wesolowska et al., 2014

VULNERABLE (VU)

Afrarchaea cornutus Lotz, 2003
Afrarchaea ngomensis Lotz, 1996
Austrachelas incertus Lawrence, 1938
Brachytheliscus bicolor Pocock, 1897
Calommata transvaalica Hewitt, 1916
Ceratogyrus paulseni Gallon, 2005
Diores dowsetti Jocqué, 1990
Erigonops littoralis (Hewitt, 1915)
Euophrys bifida Wesolowska et al., 2014
Fuchibotulus bicornis Haddad & Lyle, 2008
Galeosoma robertsi Hewitt, 1916
Griswoldia melana (Lawrence, 1938)
Hortipes atalante Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Hortipes coccinatus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Hortipes merwei Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Idiops pretoriae (Pocock, 1898)

VULNERABLE (cont.)

Ilisoa knysna Griswold, 1987
Isicabu zuluensis Griswold, 1987
Loxosceles speluncarum Simon, 1893
Massagris natalensis Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009
Moggridgea terricola Simon, 1903
Mystaria lindaicapensis Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014
Pionothele straminea Purcell, 1902
Psammoduon arenicola (Simon, 1910)
Quamtana embuleni Huber, 2003
Quamtana lajuma Huber, 2003
Scytodes gooldi Purcell, 1904
Spinotrachelas montanus Haddad et al., 2011
Stasimopus hewitti Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Themacrys silvicola (Lawrence, 1938)
Tyrotama soutpansbergensis Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005
Vidole helicityna Griswold, 1990
Xevioso lichmadina Griswold, 1990

NEAR THREATENED (NT)

Calommata meridionalis Fourie et al., 2011
Griswoldia punctata (Lawrence, 1942)
Panaretella distincta (Pocock, 1896)
Simorcus haddadi Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010

Tyrotama soutpansbergensis female, a Vulnerable species. Credit: Peter Webb

Mystaria lindaicapensis female, a Vulnerable species. Credit: Linda Wiese.

TABLE 3. Spider species flagged based on the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) categories of Rare (R) and Critically Rare (CR).

CRITICALLY RARE

Cangoderces lewisi Harington, 1951
Cheiramiona hogsbackensis Lotz, 2015
Crozetulus scutatus (Lawrence, 1964)
Heriaeus muizenberg Van Niekerk & D-Schoeman, 2013
Lepthyphantes rimicola Lawrence, 1964
Pterartoria cederbergensis Russell-Smith & Roberts, 2017
Quamtana leptopholcica (Strand, 1909)
Quamtana mbaba Huber, 2003
Quamtana merwei Huber, 2003
Quamtana meyeri Huber, 2003
Quamtana nandi Huber, 2003
Quamtana umzinto Huber, 2003
Quamtana nylsvley Huber, 2003
Smeringopus blyde Huber, 2012
Smeringopus lydenberg Hubert, 2012
Spermophora schoemanae Huber, 2003
Stasimopus mandelai Hendrixson & Bond, 2004

RARE

Afrarchaea neethlingi Lotz, 2017
Afroseto capensis Lyle & Haddad, 2010
Afrodrassex catharinae Haddad & Booysen, 2022
Anyphops kraussi (Pocock, 1898)
Austrachelas wassenaari Haddad *et al.*, 2009
Australutica africana Jocqué, 2008
Chinophrys trifasciata Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Chumma striata Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2017
Cyatholipus tortilis Griswold, 1987
Diores leleupi Jocqué, 1990
Diores setosus Tucker, 1920
Diores silvestris Jocqué, 1990
Diphya wesolowskiae Omelko *et al.*, 2020
Hortipes contubernalis Bossler's & Jocqué, 2000
Jocquestus incurvus Lyle & Haddad, 2018
Idiothele mira Gallon, 2010
Ilisoa conjugalis Griswold, 2001
Izithunzi capense (Simon, 1893)
Izithunzi lina Labarque *et al.*, 2017
Izithunzi productum (Purcell, 1904)
Izithunzi silvicola (Purcell, 1904)
Malaika longipes (Purcell, 1904)
Microstigmata amatola Griswold, 1985
Moggridgea intermedia Hewitt, 1913
Moggridgea teresae Griswold, 1987
Palystes martinfilmeri Croeser, 1996
Penestomus egazini Miller *et al.*, 2010

Penestomus montanus Miller *et al.*, 2010
Phanotea ceratogyna Griswold, 1994
Phanotea peringueyi Simon, 1896
Pterartoria cederbergensis Russell-Smith & Roberts, 2017
Pterinochilus lapalala Gallon & Engelbrecht, 2011
Quamtana ciliata (Lawrence, 1938)
Quamtana embuleni Huber, 2003
Quamtana entabeni Huber, 2003
Rotundrela orbiculata Jocqué, 1999
Rumburak lateripunctatus Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Rumburak mirabilis Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Tanzania striatus Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Scytodes montana Purcell, 1904
Smeringopus hanglip Huber, 2012
Smeringopus mlilwane Huber, 2012
Smeringopus ndumo Huber, 2012
Spermophora gordimeriae Huber, 2003
Spermophora peninsulae Lawrence, 1964

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As found for so many other taxa, South Africa has a remarkable diversity of spiders. The majority of species are of least concern and only a small percentage are threatened. Threats are linked to a variety of environmental changes many linked to agriculture and urbanization. However the importance of temperature and climate change in future will become more important. It is very important to monitor the population of species that are of special concern, as well as the large number of species that lack data and could not be assessed. Here the citizen scientist and platforms like iNaturalist might play an important role.

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The Beetle Crab Spiders *Mystaria* Simon, 1895, of South Africa: Observations and benefits of “Hang Feeding” (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The crab spider family (Thomisidae) represents a highly diverse group of arachnids characterised by unique feeding behaviours. Crab spiders frequently capture prey that is equal to, or several times, larger than, their body size. Given that their prey is often—although not always—a honeybee caught in mid-flight, it is evident that these spiders possess a potent toxin capable of immediately subduing their targets. Currently, little is known about the feeding behaviour of the African genus *Mystaria* Simon, 1895. This paper provides information on prey size and feeding methodologies for select *Mystaria* species, along with a discussion of the possible advantages of this behaviour.

Keywords: predation, prey size, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) sampled spiders extensively across wide geographic ranges. This initiative included requests for photographic records from the Virtual Museum, which successfully captured the remarkable and distinctive feeding behaviours of *Mystaria* species to hang while feeding (Fig. 1)(Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Mystaria Simon, 1895, is a small genus of endemic African crab spiders within the family Thomisidae. Globally, the genus is represented by 15 species, following a comprehensive taxonomic revision by Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2014). Nine of these species are recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Members of this genus are colloquially termed “beetle crab spiders” due to their compact, rounded body shapes and the dark, beetle-like colouration exhibited by certain species. *Mystaria* species are free-living plant dwellers found across various types of vegetation—including trees, shrubs, grasses, and leaf litter—and are only occasionally observed on flowers.

In this paper, we evaluate the general feeding behaviour of select South African *Mystaria* species, with a specific focus on prey-to-predator size ratios, and we provide suggestions for further study.

Predatory mechanisms in Thomisidae

Crab spiders are classic ambush predators capable of seizing large, highly active prey such as bees and flies (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kelly, 2024). Historically, the bulk of research regarding thomisid predation has focused on the flower crab spider genus *Thomisus* (Huseynov, 2007; Shwela *et al.*, 2023). Cumulative research indicates that crab spider predation relies on a complex combination of evolutionary traits:

- **Ambush Strategy:** Prey is typically seized at extremely close range, with the spider targeting the neck or thorax to minimise any chance of escape.
- **Venom Effectiveness:** The venom acts rapidly to immobilise insect prey, even when the prey item vastly exceeds the spider's physical size. Research demonstrates that this venom primarily targets the insect nervous system, disrupting normal signalling pathways and inducing rapid paralysis (Langenegger *et al.*, 2019). Structurally, the venom is a complex mixture of peptides and proteins, rich in small, cysteine-rich neurotoxic peptides that target ion channels and receptors in excitable cells. Notably, while highly lethal to insects, these toxins show negligible effects on vertebrate physiology, explaining their low impact on humans.
- **Mechanical Strength:** The enlarged front legs of many thomisids are physically adapted for gripping and restraining violently struggling prey.
- **Use of Floral Platform:** Many thomisid species utilise flowers as hunting platforms; the architectural structure of the flower stabilises both the spider and its prey during the critical moments of capture.
- **Prey Spectrum:** Their dietary range primarily spans six insect orders: Diptera (flies), Hymenoptera (bees and wasps), Lepidoptera (moths and butterflies), Orthoptera (crickets and grasshoppers), Thysanoptera (thrips), and Coleoptera.

Figure 1. *Mystaria savannensis* female from Lajuma Nature Reserve feeding on a bee while hanging from a silk thread. The bee is 4 times the spiders size. Credit: Dawn Cory Toussiant.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To evaluate feeding behaviours, we analysed all available photographic records of feeding *Mystaria* species sourced from the SANSa Virtual Museum and the iNaturalist online platform. *Mystaria* species are rare and not so commonly found and only 60 photographs were located of which only 16 images show them feeding. Because crab spiders do not chew or mechanically break down their prey, the outer exoskeleton of the prey item remains entirely intact, allowing for accurate taxonomic identification (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kelly, 2024). For each record, the relative sizes of the prey and the spider were documented, alongside detailed observations of how the spider manipulated its prey during consumption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General morphology: *Mystaria* are notably small spiders; adult females measure between 4 and 5 mm, while males range from 2 to 3 mm. Their abdomens feature vibrant patterns of yellow, red, black, or brown (Figs 1–5). Morphologically, they resemble small beetles, possessing a carapace that is circular to cube-shaped and an abdomen that is circular to oval and disproportionately large relative to the carapace. Males are sexually dimorphic (Figs 4–5); though they share a structural resemblance to females, they are smaller and typically feature a uniform dark shade of black, brown, orange, or copper-red. These base colours are accompanied by yellow, orange, or copper-red patterns, or they may alternatively be tinted black (Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Mystaria displays distinct morphological differences from some other typical Thomisidae genera, such as *Thomisus*, in which the front legs are significantly stronger and longer than the hind legs and bear paired, robust spines on the tibiae to grab and restrain struggling prey (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983). In contrast, all legs of *Mystaria* are slender, and the front pair entirely lacks these paired tibial spines (Figs 2–3).

Ecologically: *Mystaria* species are plant dwellers but are far less integrated into floral microhabitats than *Thomisus* species. Instead, trees, shrubs, and grasses are where they are predominantly observed, with several species sampled directly from the high canopy of indigenous forests. Adult *Mystaria* because of their small size, can use ballooning as a dispersal method. This is unusual for mature individuals of most crab spiders.

Distribution: The 15 known species of *Mystaria* are strictly endemic to the African continent. Their recorded geographical range is expansive, stretching from Ethiopia in East Africa, through the Republic of Guinea in West Africa, downward along the eastern coastline, and terminating in the Western Cape Province of South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026).

The nine species native to South Africa are predominantly concentrated in the eastern regions of the country. Currently, they are entirely unrecorded in the Northern Cape and the Free State. Regional density is highest in KwaZulu-Natal (eight recorded species) and the Eastern Cape (six recorded species). Across these regions, they have been successfully sampled from diverse ecosystems, including coastal beaches, estuaries, rivers, wetlands, and dense forest zones (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Figures 2–5. *Mystaria rufolimbata*. 1–2. Females showing different colour variants. 4–5. Female with small male on her abdomen waiting to mate. Credits: 2. Desirée Pelser. 3. Peter Webb. 4–5. Cindy Els.

Feeding behaviour (Figs 6–20)

In this paper we examined the general feeding behaviour of some *Mystaria* species in South Africa with a special focus on prey handling.

***Mystaria* species involved:** Photographs of 15 females with prey in their chelicerae were available. Of the nine species known from South Africa six species were identified with prey: *Mystaria irritatrix* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (3 records); *M. lindaicapensis* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (1); *M. mnyama* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (1); *M. occidentalis* (Millot, 1942) (1); *M. rufolimbata* Simon, 1895 (4) and *M. savannensis* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (5).

Bite sites: They usually seize their prey in the neck region (80%), while only in three photographs (Figs 13, 16, 19) the prey was caught on the body and in one the prey were caught ventrally in the neck area (Figs 14 & 21).

Prey species: They catch prey mainly from the following insect orders: Diptera (flies), Hymenoptera (bees and wasps), Thysanoptera (thrips). Bees were the most commonly caught prey, comprising more than 66.6% of the total number observed.

Prey size: As ambush predators they hide on vegetation, patiently waiting for prey. When the opportunity arises, they will pounce on their prey with lightning-fast speed. Prey are seized and although they have weak chelicerae, they secrete potent venom which allows them to attack prey larger than themselves and stop prey from struggling or flying away (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kelly, 2024). The venom very quickly immobilizes the prey and this also allows them to catch prey up to four times their size. In the available images of *Mystaria* images only two spiders were observed feeding on small prey. In the remaining the prey varies in length from 3–4 times that of the spiders length.

Handling of prey: Feeding on prey while hanging from a silk thread was for the first time observed in *Mystaria* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015). In this series 53% of the spiders were found hanging from a thread that must be strong enough to carry the weight of spider and prey.

Figure 6–20. *Mystaria* species. 6. *M. irmatrix* (Len de Beer). 7. *M. irmatrix* (Henry de Lange). 8. *M. savannensis* (Philip Carsten). 9. *M. irmatrix* (Lou-Nita Roux). 10. *M. rufolimbata* (Robert Taylor). 11. *M. rufolimbata* (Jade Hasting). 12. *M. savannensis* (John Wilkinson). 13. *M. mnyama* (Elize Geraghty). 14. *M. rufolimbata* (Desirée Pelsler). 15. *M. rufolimbata* (Charissa de Lange). 16. *M. occidentalis* (Len de Beer). 17. *M. savannensis* (John Wilkinson). 18. *M. lindacapensis* (Sally Adam). 19. *M. savannensis* (Philip Carsten). 20. *M. rufolimbata* (Dylan Leonard).

The "Hang Feeding" Hypothesis

Mystaria species can be seen hanging on a thread while feeding. While the exact evolutionary origin of *Mystaria*'s unique feeding behaviour requires deeper field validation, our photographic analyses allow us to propose the following functional hypotheses:

1. Resource and energy economy

Ambush predation provides a low-cost lifestyle in terms of time, energy, and metabolic material (silk) when contrasted with the exhausting demands of constructing conventional, temporary orb webs. In wind-dominated, unstable environments, hanging from a single silk thread offers a highly reliable hunting framework. Constructing a fragile, stationary orb-web in these microhabitats would be highly hazardous and inefficient, as the constant movement of surrounding foliage would repeatedly compromise the web's structural integrity.

2. Predator avoidance

By eschewing large, highly visible orb-webs, *Mystaria* individuals remain concealed from predators such as wasps and birds that visually scan dense foliage for webs and spiders during early morning and daylight hours.

3. Increased safety from dangerous prey

Photographic evidence consistently reveals a highly precise bite location situated directly behind the head of captured bees. This localised envenomation likely facilitates neurotoxic access to the central nervous system. Simultaneously, the specialised strategy of attacking and subsequently feeding while suspended in mid-air allows the spider to maintain a secure physical distance from its prey. This suspension drastically minimises the risk of mechanical injury to the spider from larger, vigorously struggling insects (Fig. 21).

4. Specialized hunting strategy

Although real-time field observations of active hunting remain scarce, evidence suggests that *Mystaria* can intercept and seize insects mid-flight. Alternatively, they may pounce on insects that land haphazardly near their ambush site while remaining securely tethered to the host plant by a structural silk line.

5. Minimizing inter-species kleptoparasitic competition

In Fig. 22 a *Mystaria* species is seen attached to one end of a prey item while jackal flies (Milichiidae) simultaneously draw haemolymph from the opposite end. Hang-feeding in windy, aerial environments may afford the spider a few undisputed, isolated moments with its catch. This extra time may prevent immediate competition by agile kleptoparasites that would otherwise disrupt the meal in a stable environment. The net energy conserved or gained through this undisturbed feeding window may directly influence survival margins.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study presents preliminary insights into the enigmatic predatory behaviours of the African endemic beetle crab spider genus *Mystaria*. While traditional research within the family Thomisidae has heavily favoured flower-dwelling genera like *Thomisus*, our analysis of photographic records from the SANSA Virtual Museum and iNaturalist underscores that *Mystaria* has developed unique ecological and morphological specialisations. Despite lacking the robust tibial setae typically used by other thomisids to mechanically restrain struggling prey, *Mystaria* successfully targets and subdues highly active insects—such as honeybees—that are equal to or several times their body size.

Figure 21–22. *Mystaria* species. 21. *M. mnyama* female almost invisible while feeding on a bee (Elize Geraghty). 22. *M. rufolimbata* female feeding with jackal flies (Milichiidae) simultaneously drawing haemolymph from the bee (Bruce Blake).

Our findings support the "hang-feeding" hypothesis as a highly adaptive evolutionary strategy. By utilising a precise bite site directly behind the prey's head, *Mystaria* leverages a potent neurotoxin to induce rapid immobilisation. Suspended safely by a structural silk thread, the spider effectively neutralises the physical risks associated with manipulating large, struggling prey.

Furthermore, this unique aerial suspension strategy provides clear ecological advantages: it minimises energy expenditures in wind-dominated environments where building traditional orb webs is structurally unfeasible, reduces visibility to avian predators, and offers a critical buffer against immediate competition from kleptoparasitic jackal flies.

Ultimately, these observations expand our understanding of diversity within thomisid hunting strategies. Because this framework relies on photographic data, future field-based research and real-time behavioural studies are essential to fully validate these hunting mechanics and clarify the precise origins of this fascinating, specialised behaviour.

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The Cyrtarachninae genera of South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily of orb-weavers of the family Araneidae represented by two tribes. It is considered one of the most specialised lineages of orb-weavers, and seven genera and 13 species are currently recorded from South Africa. In the tribe Cyrtarachnini, a reduced-web lineage is evident, represented by a strong visual masquerade, as seen in the following genera in South Africa: *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902; *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868; *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 and *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895. In the tribe Mastophorini, the orb-web is abandoned entirely, and three genera are recorded from South Africa: *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910; *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895 and *Pycnacantha* (Fabricius, 1781). The 13 species recorded from South Africa are illustrated and discussed.

Keywords: behaviour, biodiversity, Cyrtarachnini, Mastophorini, spanning-web, South African National Survey of Arachnida, taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), spiders have been widely sampled over the years, and several Cyrtarachninae genera have been recorded. Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily of orb-weaver spiders of the family Araneidae (Scharff & Coddington, 1997). It is considered one of the most specialised lineages of orb-weavers, with significant modifications to prey capture that frequently target moths. This involved moth specialisation, unusual web architecture, and strong use of masquerade and chemical deception. It was first established by Simon (1892) as Cyrtarachneae and has since been treated at taxonomic ranks such as tribes or subfamilies (Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014).

SUBFAMILY CYRTARACHNINAE

Common morphological traits of these spiders include large abdomens in adult females, often overhanging the cephalothorax, and elongated, strong legs used for prey capture. There is strong sexual size dimorphism, with the male being much smaller and of a different shape. The key defining behaviour of Cyrtarachninae are:

a. Web reduction in prey capture: Unlike typical orb-weavers, some Cyrtarachninae build highly reduced webs with few capture threads known as “spanning-thread” webs (Stowe, 1986). It consists of reduced capture spirals of which the threads are widely spaced, with large aggregate glue droplets relative to those of typical orb-weavers (Figs 9–11). However, some species do not use a web at all; instead, they capture prey with a bola consisting of a single silk line with a sticky droplet (Figs 42 & 54). While a few species are completely webless, hanging with spread out legs to grab prey flying past (Figs 75 & 76).

b. Moth specialisation and chemical mimicry: Many members are moth specialists, overcoming moths’ anti-adhesive wing scales by producing exceptionally sticky aggregate silk that attaches to moth scales (Eberhard, 1977). In some species, the spider emits female moth sex pheromones, sometimes multiple compounds simultaneously, actively luring prey directly into striking range.

c. Masquerade (visual mimicry of objects): Cyrtarachninae are classic examples of masquerade, where the adult females often resemble bird droppings, snails, seeds, or other inanimate objects. This allows them to remain exposed on vegetation during the day without danger of being attacked.

Molecular phylogenetic work shows that Cyrtarachninae split into two major evolutionary clades. Together, they form one of the most striking examples of adaptive radiation within orb-weaving spiders.

SUBFAMILY CYRTARACHNINAE

Tribe Cyrtarachnini

1. *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868

C. ixoides (Simon, 1870)
C. finniganae Lessert, 1936
C. termitophila Lawrence, 1952

2. *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867

P. thorntoni (Blackwall, 1865)
P. walleri (Blackwall, 1865)

3. *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895

P. dippenaarae Roff & Haddad, 2015

4. *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902

A. olivaceus Pocock, 1902
A. pani Lessert, 1930

Tribe Mastophorini

1. *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895

C. akermani Hewitt, 1923
C. debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004
C. longipes (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)

2. *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910

A. seydeli Giltay, 1935

3. *Pycnacantha* Blackwall, 1865

P. tribulus (Fabricius, 1781)

I. TRIBE CYRTARACHNINI

Cyrtarachnini is one of the principal groupings within Cyrtarachninae, especially in narrower taxonomic treatments. These spiders typically retain some form of reduced web or triangular webs but do not use bolas. They are not known to rely strongly on pheromone mimicry. In South Africa they show strong visual masquerade, particularly insect or bird-dropping mimicry. Four genera meet the requirement of Cyrtarachnini: *Cyrtarachne* (Fig. 1); *Paraplectana* (Fig. 2); *Pasilobus* (Fig. 3) and *Aethriscus* (Fig. 4).

Figures 1–4. Cyrtarachninae, tribe Cyrtarachnini. 1. *Cyrtarachne ixoides* (Allen Jones). 2. *Paraplectana thorntoni* (Les Oates). 3. *Pasilobus dippenaarae* (Steve Goodall). 4. *Aethriscus olicaceus* (Les Oates).

1. *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868

Cyrtarachne Thorell, 1868 is represented by 56 species found worldwide (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are found mainly in tropical and subtropical regions (Asia, Africa, and other warm areas). They typically live on plants in forests and humid environments.

The females are 5–8 mm long, while males are much smaller (2–3 mm). In females, the abdomen is shiny with a triangular shape. In males, the abdomen is smaller and darker in colour.

These spiders are mostly nocturnal. During the day, they are found on vegetation, resembling bird droppings. Their modified spanning-thread web is made in the vegetation. They prey on flying insects that get stuck to the loosely spun threads bearing adhesive glue droplets. The spider then pulls the prey toward itself like a fishing line. Three species are known from South Africa

Cyrtarachne ixoides (Simon, 1870) (Figs 5–12)

Cyrtarachne ixoides was described in 1870 by Simon as *Peltosoma ixoides*. It has a wide global distribution and has been recorded from the Mediterranean basin to Georgia, Madagascar and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). In 2008, it was first recorded in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008) and is currently recorded across all provinces except the Northern Cape (Fig. 12).

The female abdomen is large, shiny, and triangular or dome-shaped, with a white anterior border (Fig. 5). Therefore, the species is commonly known as the white-banded bird-dropping spider. In the males, the abdomen is smaller and darker in colour (Fig. 6). They produce a spanning-web (Figs 7, 9–11). It is presently known from eight provinces in South Africa (Fig. 12) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones, 2008; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a). The epigyne is egg-shaped (Fig. 8).

Figures 5–12. *Cyrtarachne ixoides*. 5. Female (Len de Beer). 6. Male. 7. Female ventral view (Allen Jones). 8. Epigyne (after Bosselaers, 2018). 9–11. Female with prey in spanning-web (Allen Jones). 12. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red spot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black spot from SANSA database.

Cyrtarachne finniganae Lessert, 1936 (Figs 13–14)

The male (3 mm) (Fig. 13) was described from Mozambique and was recorded for the first time from Gauteng and Limpopo in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2026b) (Fig. 14). Little is known about their behaviour, and the female is still unknown.

Cyrtarachne termitophila Lawrence, 1952 (Figs 15–16)

The male (2 mm) (Fig. 15) was described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo and was recorded for the first time from Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal in South Africa in 2026 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2026a) (Fig. 16). Little is known about their behaviour and the female is still unknown.

2. *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867

Paraplectana Brito Capello was described in 1867 and currently includes 13 species from Africa and Asia (World Spider Catalog, 2026). The species are easy to recognise by their round, dome-shaped abdomen that nearly covers the carapace. The surface of the abdomen is smooth and shiny and decorated with very bright reds, oranges, pinks and yellow spots. Colour morphs are seen in both species. Currently, two species have been identified from South Africa, but more undescribed species have been noted (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

They build modified orb-webs called “spanning-thread webs,” which have been observed in South Africa for *P. thornntoni* (Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2022) and *P. walleri* (Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2020). They are nocturnal, and during the day they remain on vegetation, relying on their resemblance to ladybird beetles to avoid detection by predators. Because of their appearance, they are commonly called “ladybird spider”. It is a good example of Batesian mimicry, as it mimics the bad-tasting ladybird beetles that predators, like birds avoid.

Paraplectana thornntoni (Blackwall, 1865) (Figs 17–23)

Paraplectana thornntoni (Blackwall, 1865) is an African endemic species described as *Eurysoma thornntoni* from Mozambique. The species is known from seven African countries (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022b). In South Africa, it is widely distributed in six provinces (Fig. 23).

The female is recognised by the red abdominal markings (Figs 17–19), but some specimens are also yellow (Fig. 20) or a mix. They construct a spanning-web (Figs 21 & 22) (Du Preez & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2022; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). The male is still unknown.

Figures 17–23. *Paraplectana thornntoni*. 17. Female on a small silk disk on leaf (Kobie du Preez). 18. Female (Les Oates). 19. Female with the beetle they mimic (Susan Dippenaar). 20. A female with yellow markings (Jolandie Buck). 21–22. Female in spanning-web (Kobie du Preez). 23. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown with red dot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black dot from SANSA database.

Paraplectana walleri (Blackwall, 1865) (Figs 24–30)

Paraplectana walleri is an African endemic described by Blackwall (1865) as *Eurysoma walleri* from Mozambique. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa it has been recorded mainly from the eastern parts of South Africa: Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape (Fig. 30).

The colour of the female varies from yellow (Figs 26 & 28), orange (Figs 24 & 25) to almost red (Fig. 27). They construct a spanning-web (Figs 28 & 29) as discussed by Cooper & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2020).

Figures 24–30. *Paraplectana walleri*. 24–25. Female dorsal view and ventral view (Guy Johnston). 26. Anterior view (Paul van Rensburg). 27. Female dorsal view (Meg Cumming). 28–29. Female in spanning-web (Morah Cooper). 30. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown with red dot as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black dot from SANSA database.

3. *Pasilobus* Simon, 1895

Pasilobus Simon, 1895 was described in 1895, and is currently known from 14 species recorded from Africa, South and Southeast Asia and parts of Australasia (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are recognized by their mottled, shiny triangular shaped abdomens.

Pasilobus is best known for its radically modified prey-capture web. The web is triangular, not circular, and consists of three framework radii: a central midline thread and widely spaced spanning threads hanging from it. These threads hang down like loose lines or strands with sticky droplets.

Pasilobus dippenarae Roff & Haddad, 2015 (Figs 31–35)

Pasilobus dippenarae is endemic to KwaZulu-Natal described in 2015 from Hilton. The female's carapace is partially hidden under the flattened, triangular-shaped abdomen (Figs 31–33). The abdomen is broad, often twice as wide as long, with low tubercles or

lobes. Legs are slender and relatively long, and the anterior pair is folded sideways (Fig. 32). Roff & Haddad (2015) described the species and discussed their general behaviour (Fig. 34). The species have been sampled from several localities around Pietermaritzburg, Kloof and Durban (Fig. 34).

Figures 31–35. *Pasilobus dippenarae*. 31–32. Female dorsal view (Steve Goodall). 33. Orange colour variant (John Roff). 34. The egg sac (John Roff). 35. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

4. *Aethriscus* Pocock, 1902

Aethriscus Pocock (1902) is endemic to Africa, and known from two species (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They are rare spiders, and both species are known from South Africa. Apparently, *Aethriscus* is one of the least understood species in the Cyrtarachninae group.

They build a very reduced spanning-thread web. The web has few sticky threads designed for intercepting flying prey, mainly moths. They are nocturnal and, during the day, sit exposed on vegetation, blending in and resembling a bird dropping.

Aethriscus olivaceus Pocock, 1902 (Figs 36–38)

Aethriscus olivaceus is an African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo by Pocock (1902). The body has a triangular shape. The abdomen is dark with humps; the posterior area has a white triangular patch. Legs short, folded around the body. Little is known about their behaviour. When not active, they rest on vegetation and resemble bird droppings (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a). They have been recorded from the Eastern Cape, Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 38).

Figures 36–38. *Aethriscus olivaceus*. 36. Female dorsal view (Les Oates). 37. Female (Nicky Scott). 38. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

Aethriscus pani Lessert, 1930 (Figs 39-40)

Aethriscus pani is a rare African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo by Lessert (1930). It was recorded for the first time from South Africa in 2026. The female is tawny, smooth and shiny, and the abdomen is twice as wide as it is long, and the legs are the same colour as the carapace (Leroy *et al.*, 2026). Little is known about their behaviour.

Figures 39–40. *Aethriscus pani*. 39. Female (Sharpview). 40. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black.

II. TRIBE MASTOPHORINI (Figs 41–43)

Mastophorini refers to a group of spiders that have abandoned the orb-web entirely. This includes cases where females use a bola or hang from a thread, grabbing prey as it flies past. These spiders possibly emit female moth sex pheromones, sometimes multiple compounds simultaneously, actively luring prey directly into striking range.

In South Africa, the tribe is represented by *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910 (1 sp.), *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895 (3 spp.) and *Pycnacantha* Blackwall, 1865 (1 sp.). *Pycnacantha* is listed here in the tribe Mastophorini. It meets the requirement of the tribe, namely the absence of a web.

Figures 41–43. 41. Female *Acantharachne* (Peter Webb). 42. Female *Cladomelea* with bolas (Len de Beer). 43. Female *Pycnacantha* (Les Oates).

1. *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910

The genus *Acantharachne* was erected by Tullgren in 1910 for the species *Acantharachne cornuta* from Tanzania. The genus is represented by eight species and is known only from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Members of *Acantharachne* received little to no attention since their description, and unfortunately, little is known about their behaviour. Because they are so rare the genus was not included in the phylogenetic study of the orb-weaving spider family Araneidae (Scharff *et al.*, 2020).

Emerit (2000) suggested that the Malagasy species may use a bolas to forage, although there are no direct observations supporting this implied hunting strategy. Only one species is known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022c).

Acantharachne seydeli Giltay, 1935 (Figs 44–50)

Acantharachne seydeli was described by Giltay, 1935 from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It was first recorded in South Africa by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2022c). The female has a large, globular abdomen relative to the carapace. The carapace is broader than long and mottled (cream to brown with darker markings), bearing small tubercles (Fig. 44).

The abdomen has two large circular dorsal humps on the lateral edge. The humps have numerous blunt tubercles dorsally (Figs 45–47). Front legs are slightly longer and folded forward in front of the chelicerae when resting. Overall appearance resembles bird droppings, a form of defensive mimicry. The specimens sampled rest on the upper surfaces of leaves, while a female from Limpopo was collected during fogging of the savannah trees.

Figures 44–50. *Acantharachne seydeli*. 44–45. Female from Kloof (Andrea Sander). 46. Female from Gauteng (Nicky Scott). 47. Line drawing after Giltray (1935). 48–49. Female from Wakefield (Peter Webb). 50. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as downloaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSa database in black.

2. *Cladomelea* Simon, 1895

Cladomelea Simon, 1895, are endemic to the Afrotropical Region, and three of the four species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). They have a highly derived hunting method using bolas. The females are broad-bodied with round abdomens, and the carapace features long, horn-like outgrowths (Fig. 66). Sexual dimorphism with males differing in shape and size (Fig. 70).

The females do not build an orb-web. Instead, they use a highly specialized hunting strategy swinging sticky silk droplet to capture flying insects, usually moths. Many species attract moths using chemical mimicry (Eberhard, 1977). This web reduction is accompanied by highly adhesive silk used on the bolas.

Cladomelea akermani Hewitt, 1923 (Figs 51–58)

Cladomelea akermani is a KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Hewitt (1923) from Pietermaritzburg, based on a female. The male was described by Leroy *et al.* (1998). Female with body and legs yellow-brown (Figs 51–53). Carapace hirsute, with three long, sharp-tipped tubercles (Fig. 55). Abdomen with rows of small tubercles each bearing tufts of setae (Fig. 55). Front legs long and densely covered with long, thin setae (Fig. 51). Male very small (Fig. 52, see arrow) with body and legs chestnut brown.

The spider constructs a reduced orb-web consisting of a bolas line used to catch moths at night. Several people have reported on their behaviour (Akerman, 1923; Leroy *et al.*, 1998). Diaz & Roff (2022) observed that *C. akermani* actively spins its body while swinging the bolas. They found that when activity occurs in an open environment, it creates turbulent air, spreading pheromones farther and creating a pocket of pheromones. They are found towards the end of the summer and into autumn. The egg sacs are attached to grass stems (Fig. 53) (Leroy *et al.*, 1998).

Figures 51–58. *Cladomelea akermani*. 51. Female dorsal view. 52. Female with very small male (See arrow). 53. Female with egg sacs. 54. Female with bolas. 55. Female colour variant. 56. Epigyne. 57. Male. 58. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black. Credits: 51–54. John Roff. 55. Sunčana Bradley. 56–57. After Leroy *et al.* (1998).

Cladomelea debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004 (Figs 59–64)

Cladomelea debeeri is endemic to South Africa. The female carapace is yellowish-brown, decorated with dark brown patterns and covered with long, white, woolly setae. Abdomen is fawn triangular, with an intricate pattern, each corner studded with five prominent tubercles (Figs 59-60); each tubercle bearing a tuft of long white setae (Fig. 61). Legs creamish brown with dark spiralling bands; legs without strong setae but bearing dense long, hair-like setae (Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

The bolas-line consisted of a three-strand thread held together with three droplets, positioned one above the other. Each droplet was approximately 2–3 mm in diameter. The spider used its fourth leg to hold onto a trapeze-line. The bolas-line was then whirled at intervals, using the second pair of legs. Initially, the whirling happened at intervals of about five minutes, but later became more frequent,

Figures 59–64. *Cladomelea debeeri*. 59. Female. 60–61. Female showing the abdominal pattern. 62. Female preparing the bolas. 63. Epigyne. 64. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black. Credits: 59. Sunčana Bradley. 60–61. John Roff. 62. Len de Beer.

Cladomelea longipes (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) (Figs 65–73)

A female of *C. longipes* was described by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877 from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It is known from several African countries. It was first recorded in South Africa by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019) while Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal (2020) provided more information on the very small, dark male (Figs 70–71). The female abdomen is triangular, dorsally pink, and infused with a grey guanophore and silky hair. Two large, yellow, and round tubercles are present on the antero-lateral corners of the abdomen, and four smaller white, round tubercles are arranged in rows between small white tubercles (Figs 65–66).

They make a bolas and swing it around (Fig. 67). During the observation period, only moths were caught. While observing the female feeding on a moth another moth landed on them. An indication that it possibly been attracted by pheromones of the captured moth or false pheromone of the spider (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal, 2020). The egg cocoon differ from that of other known *Cladomelea* species (Fig. 69).

Figures 65–72. *Cladomelea longipes*. 66. Female dorsal view. 66. Female showing the long tubercles on the carapace. 67. Female with bolas. 68. Epigyne. 69. Female with egg sac. 70. Female with small male. 71. Male. 72. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and from SANSA database in black. Credits: 65. Meg Cumming. 66-67, 69, 70-71, 69. Tinus Odendaal.

3. Pycnacantha Blackwall, 1865

An African genus described by Blackwall (1865) and represented by four species from Cameroon, Madagascar, Mozambique, Namibia, and South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2026). Meise (1932), who reviewed the genus and described two species, noted that the female of *Pycnacantha* resemble the fruit of *Tribulus terrestris*, an annual plant in the caltrop family (Zygophyllaceae) known for its strong spikes. They are also known as hedgehog spiders.

***Pycnacantha tribulus* (Fabricius, 1781) (Figs 74–80)**

The female *P. tribulus* are found in grasses and low vegetation (Fig. 73). Their spiky bodies and colouration allow the spiders to blend in with grass, particularly *Themeda* and *Cymbopogon* species that have spiky seeds. The spiders rest on the grass during the day and, in the evening, spin a triangular trapezium web between two adjacent grass stems. Here they hang upside down, with legs outstretched, trying to capture flying insects (Figs 74–76). These spiders are suspected of producing mimetic pheromones that attract male moths, which they grasp with their forelegs before feeding (Fig. 77). Egg sacs are attached to vegetation (Fig. 78)(Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy, 1996; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024). The species is widely distribution throughout South Africa (Fig. 79).

Figures 73–80. *Pycnacantha tribulus*. 73. Female. 74–76. Female hanging from a trapezium web with extended front legs waiting for prey. 77. Female with a moth. 78. Female with egg sac. 79. Distribution of the species including the iNaturalist records shown in red as down loaded on 26 May 2026 and black from SANSA database. Credits: 74. Allen Jones. 74–76. Peter Webb. 77–78. Les Oates.

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An updated review of the polymorphic crab spider *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875

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ABSTRACT: *Thomisus spinifer* O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from specimens from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was preoccupied, rendering it invalid. *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875) based on a female specimen from the southern side of the Pyrenees, between France and Spain, became the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer*. But the nomenclatural history of the species is complex, involving multiple synonyms. In the description of *T. citrinellus*, an irregular triangular marking and short transverse bands on the abdomen are distinctive for the species, and the legs have bands and spots. These markings correspond with observations of the species by different authors throughout Africa. With more than 100 photographs available of live spiders, at least two colour morphs in shades of pink or brown are seen.

Keywords: biodiversity, colour change, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Thomisus spinifer O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from a specimen collected from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was already preoccupied, rendering it invalid according to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). The species *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875), has become the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer* (Roewer, 1955) and is listed as such in the World Spider Catalog (2026), with verified taxonomic standing in the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS). However, its nomenclatural history is complex, involving multiple synonyms. *Thomisus citrinellus* was described from a female sampled from “Pyrénées espagnoles” an area on the southern side of the Pyrenees mountain range between France and Spain. The World Spider Catalog (2026) listed *T. citrinellus* as widely distributed across Spain, France, Cyprus, Turkey, Africa, Seychelles, Yemen (incl. Socotra), Israel, and Iraq and possibly Iran. In this paper the presence of *T. citrinellus* in Africa is reviewed with notes on the different colour morphs found.

METHODS

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), many *T. citrinellus* specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled, and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). As part of the SANSA Virtual Museum photograph database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) numerous images were received that provided additional information on the species. Images of the species was also sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform.

RESULTS

***Thomisus spinifer* records from Africa:** Publications indicate that *T. citrinellus* has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983) revised the *Thomisus* species of southern Africa, and examined numerous specimens from Africa housed in several museums abroad. *Thomisus citrinellus* are presently reported from: Algeria (Beladjal *et al.*, 2025); Botswana (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kassimatis, 2002); Chad (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Egypt (Sallam, 2012); Djibouti (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989); Ethiopia (Caporiacco, 1941; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); French Guinea (Millot, 1942); Kenya (Caporiacco, 1949; Kioko *et al.*, 2021); Mali (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Mozambique (Lessert, 1936); Namibia (NCA); Senegal (Simon, 1886; Caporiacco, 1941); South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Tanzania (Russell-Smith, 2020); Uganda (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983) and Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

Figures 1–2. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 1. Female from Heidelberg in Gauteng. 2. Male from Hoedspruit. Credits: 1. Johan van Zyl. 2. Peter Webb.

Figure 3–7. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 3. Female habitus from French Guinea. 4. Epigyne. 5. Female habitus from South Africa. 6. Epigyne. 7. *Thomisus citrinellus* female, first record from eSwatini. Credits: 3–4. After Millot (1942). 5–6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). 7. Phil White.

Female diagnostic characters: Simon (1875) described the holotype female, noting abdominal markings consisting of an irregular triangular dark mark followed by short transverse bands, and mentions the bands and spots on the legs. This corresponds to the markings shown in Fig. 1. Only in 1886 did Simon mention the darker mediolateral bands on the carapace of a female from Senegal. In the same paper, he provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15). Both Lessert (1936), with specimens from Mozambique, and Caporiacco (1941), with specimens from Senegal and Ethiopia, observed the dark mediolateral bands on the carapace, the bands on the anterior legs, and the markings on the abdomen. Millot (1942) provided the first illustrations of a female from French Guinea (Figs 4 & 5). He clearly illustrated the abdominal markings as described by Simon (1875). But due to the complex nomenclatural history, the invalidity of *T. spinifer*, the subspecies *T. spinifer decorata* (Millot, 1942); *T. spinifer simoni*, *T. spinifer obscurus* and *T. spinifer maculata* Caporiacco (1941; 1949) were regarded as synonyms of *T. citrinellus* by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

Colour morphs: In museum specimens or alcohol-collected individuals, pink pigments may degrade post-mortem, appearing fawn to brown (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025b). This is especially relevant when comparing live vs preserved colouration. With more than 100 images of live *T. citrinellus* available, two colour morphs have been recognised.

A few specimens are fawn with brown markings (Figs 15–17), while the majority are white with pink markings (Figs 1, 8–14). The pink colouration in *T. citrinellus* is primarily due to stable, lipochrome pigments in the hypodermis, rather than reversible pigment dynamics like those seen in yellow-white transitions of other *Thomisus* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a). The pink colour is more persistent and not withdrawn or redistributed like ommochromes (yellow pigments). The cuticle and hypodermis are partially transparent, allowing pink pigments to interact with underlying guanine crystals. These markings are not known to change with background, supporting their role as fixed traits (Gawryszewski *et al.*, 2015; Herberstein & Gawryszewski, 2012). Lipochromes that accumulate in hypodermal cells form the characteristic markings as described by Simon (1875; 1886). This pink colouration tends to intensify with age (Fig. 14), suggesting a developmental trajectory rather than an environmentally induced change. Brown colouration sometimes replaces pink in *T. citrinellus*. It could be melanin accumulation that overrides lighter pigments, turning pink to brown or ommochrome degradation that may also result in brownish tones replacing pink.

If pink is derived from unstable pigments (e.g. ommochromes or carotenoids), it may fade or oxidise into brown under certain conditions. Brown may be favoured in habitats with leaf litter, grasses, and bark, which offer better camouflage (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a).

Figure 8–14. Examples of pink morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 8. Peter Webb. 9. Sally Adam. 10. Lynette Rudmann. 11. Les Oates. 12. Cecile Roux. 13. Andrea Sander. 14. S. Boyd.

Figure 15–17. Examples of brown morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 15. Linda Wiese. 16. Vida van der Walt. 17. Andrea Sander.

Figure 15–18. *Thomisus citrinellus* male. 15. Male palp drawing after Simon (1886) from Senegal. 16. Male habitus after Millot (1942). 17. Male palp after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1989). 18. Male (Ian Anderson).

Male: The male is much smaller than the female. Simon (1886) provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15), which corresponds to that of Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983; 1989) (Fig. 17). The palp is very distinctive as it bears two slightly curved retrolateral apophyses on the palpal tibia and a large downward-inclined tegulum. In the male (Figs 1, 16 & 18), the carapace is brown and covered with long erect setae. Legs with front legs brown, tibiae I and II darker brown with metatarsi with a faint darker band that varies between specimens; posterior legs pale brown. The abdomen is covered with numerous erect setae. However, the bodies of males of several species resemble each other; sometimes, only bands on the front legs vary. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species is to examine the male palp. Also, assuming that males found on females' abdomens are the same species as the females is not always correct, as they are frequently killed by females.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thomisus citrinellus is a common species and is currently known from 19 African countries. The female is recognised by the mediolateral bands on the carapace and, on the abdomen, an irregular triangular marking followed by short, wavy posterior bands. The abdomen sometimes has a round, dark spot on each tubercle. In the male several species resemble each other; sometimes, only differing by the bands on the front legs. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species correctly is to examine the male palp. Also, males found on females' abdomens are not always of the same species, and they are then killed (Fig. 21).

With the large number of images available, two colour morphs, pink or brown, have been identified. However most specimens are pink, and the darker body markings are present in all, but do vary in shape (Figs 7-14). *Thomisus citrinellus* seems not to change colour as observed in some other *Thomisus* species.

This was also observed by Levy (1973), who reported that the species is unable to change colour. However, we observed some variations in body patterns. In Fig. 19, the colouration is dark and possibly melanin based. Melanistic morphs in Thomisidae are possibly underreported due to seasonal, sexual, or ontogenetic variation (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a) but have been observed in several thomisid genera. In Fig. 20, the female has all the pink markings but with a yellow undertone.

With further research and more information now available, *Thomisus ghesquierei* Lessert, 1943, as reported on by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023), might in reality be the brown morph of *T. citrinellus*. However, specimens are needed to study genitalia for confirmation.

Figure 19. *Thomisus citrinellus* female dark variation (Heather and Andrew Hodgson)

Figure 20. *Thomisus citrinellus* female with yellow tint (Vida vd Walt)

Figure 21. *Thomisus citrinellus* female feeding on a male that is not conspecific.

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First records of *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930, was described from the Democratic Republic of Congo based on a single female. Here we report on a female from South Africa for the first time. The general morphology and distribution of the species is discussed with notes on its lifestyle. The male is still unknown.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Aethriscus Pocock, 1902 is a rare African genus of orb-weaver spider family Araneidae known only from two African species (World Spider Catalog, 2026). It is listed in the subfamily Cyrtarachninae in the Cyrtarachnini. Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily that is notable for its highly specialized predatory strategies, especially moth specialization, unusual web architectures, such as spanning-thread webs, triangular webs, and bolas, while some are webless with effective using masquerade and chemical deception (Stowe, 1986; Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014). The group was first established by Simon (1892), originally as Cyrtarachneae, and has since been treated at different taxonomic ranks (Sharff & Coddington 2020; *et al.*, 2014).

Little is known about the behaviour of the *Aethriscus* species, only that they are known as bird-dropping spiders. They rely on extreme crypsis and immobility when resting, resembling bird droppings. This is supported by their shiny bodies and short legs that fold around the body (Figs 1 & 4). When a spider is seen but misidentified as uninteresting by predators, it is a form of defensive mimicry called masquerade. Masquerade is a special type of protective mimicry where an organism avoids being eaten by resembling an inanimate object that predators normally ignore, such as a twig, leaf, stone, or bird dropping. The key idea is misidentification: the predator sees the organism but mistakenly identifies it as something that is not food. This enables the spiders to rest unnoticed during the day in exposed places on the upper surface of leaves.

Although *Aethriscus* is recorded from two African countries, very few specimens have been collected, and few field observations have been made. *Aethriscus olivaceus* Pocock, 1902 and *A. pani* Lessert, 1930, are known only from females, and both were described from the Democratic Republic of Congo and re-collected from South Africa. *Aethriscus olivaceus* was first reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), and in this paper, we provide the first records of *A. pani* from South Africa.

METHODS

A female *A. pani* was collected in 2026 in Gauteng and the specimen was kept alive in a large terrarium. She died and a voucher specimen is deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Institute in Pretoria. Data sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform, resulted in only one additional record (Fig. 4) from the Limpopo province.

TAXONOMY

Diagnostic characters: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 was described from Democratic Republic of Congo. Female total length 10 mm. Carapace is fawn, smooth and shiny with blackish hue; with small tubercles present at the cephalic region constriction; the carapace is wider than long with sides rounded, narrowed in eye region (Fig. 3). Eyes in two rows (Fig. 5) with the median and lateral eyes on tubercles (Figs 5 & 9) and the median eyes closely group, three times closer to each other than the laterals; anterior eyes slightly larger than posterior eyes.

Figure 1–3. *Aethriscus pani* female from Gauteng. 1. Anterior view. 2. Ventral view. 3. Dorsal view. Credit: John Leroy.

Figure 4–5. *Aethriscus pani*. 4. Female from Ohrigstad, dorsal view showing their resemblance to bird droppings. 5. Anterior view showing the eye pattern. Credits: 4. Sharpview. 5. John Leroy.

Figure 6–11. *Aethriscus pani* female. 6–7. Epigyne. 8. Habitus line drawing, dorsal view. 9. Anterior view. 10. Posterior view. 11. Ventral view. Credits: 9–11. John Leroy; 6 & 8. After Lessert (1930).

Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen smooth and shiny covering almost half of the cephalothorax; twice as wide (19 mm) as it is long (8 mm); when viewed from above, displays a triangular shape (Figs 3 & 8); anterior edge of the abdomen scalloped, decorated with three tubercles, with 11 submarginal sigilla (Fig. 9); abdomen posteriorly concave with four slightly pronounced, rounded tubercles (Figs 8 & 10); dorsum with small round to oval sigilla forming round depressions around the border as well as four on the median area (Figs 3 & 10); ventrum with strikingly wrinkled sinuous grooves around spinnerets. Legs tawny with indistinct, blackish-tinted bands with layers of short setae (Fig. 5); tibiae and metatarsi are flattened and slightly unequal, with metatarsi shorter than tibiae, tibiae I and II with a slight curve (Figs 1 & 9). Epigyne concave at the base with two oval, transverse concavities and upward-pointed scape (Figs 6 & 7). Male unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo; South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng:* Plot off Malmani Road, Cradle of Humankind, Krugersdorp (-26.03465, 27.69173). *Limpopo:* Krugerpos, Orighstad (-24.904, 30.549).

LIFESTYLE

The female specimen from Gauteng was collected at night from low bushes and grass near a bee hive with a sweepnet. She was kept in a terrarium for observation. She was active at night, spinning irregular lines of strong silk between twigs and grass. During the day she rested on the ground not on supplied vegetation. Unfortunately she died after a few days.

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1st circular

The **African Arachnological Society (AFRAS)** and the Organizing Committee are delighted to invite members of the arachnological community and accompanying guests to the **15th AFRAS Colloquium**, organized through the **DITSONG: National Museum of Natural History**, Pretoria, South Africa.

This is a wonderful opportunity for international and local arachnologists to connect and discuss potential collaborative projects on the hugely diverse African arachnid fauna.

DATES

10 – 15 January 2027

VENUE

Lapalala Wilderness School (<https://www.lwschool.org/>), about 50 km from the small town of Vaalwater in Limpopo Province, South Africa, and 3.5 hours from Johannesburg.

<https://www.lapalala.com/lapalala-wilderness-school/>

The venue is an award-winning, off-the-grid, eco-built educational facility. Constructed from rammed earth, the state-of-the-art facility harmonizes seamlessly with the bushveld, creating a fully immersive nature experience.

Comfortable accommodation ranges from private lodge-style ensuite rooms to shared dormitories with a unique one-to-one guest-to-bathroom ratio available to delegates on a first-come basis.

The Lapalala Wilderness School falls within the UNESCO-declared Waterberg Biosphere Reserve. While nested in the southeast corner of the **Big Five Lapalala Wilderness Reserve** (<https://www.lapalala.com/lapalala-wilderness/>), a secure fence separates the two properties to ensure a safe walking environment. The reserve has 73 small and large mammal and 278 bird species recorded. For arthropods, much remain to be discovered in this recognized biodiversity hotspot.

COSTS

Registration Fee: R2,850 (approx. \$175 USD) for delegates based in Africa; R3,500 (approx. \$215 USD) for delegates not based in Africa.

Accommodation and meals: Packages*, incl. 15% VAT, range from R5,060 (approx. \$300 USD) per person sharing up to R10,235 (approx. \$600 USD) for a private room. All private rooms with ensuite bathrooms.

*All packages include accommodation and meals for five nights PLUS one Big Five safari game drive.

SPONSORSHIPS

Some part- or full- sponsorships will be available. More detail to follow soon.

1st circular

TRAVEL & TRANSFERS

Airport Shuttle: Available upon request from O.R. Tambo International Airport (Johannesburg) at an additional fee.

COLLECTING

The venue is surrounded by bushveld savanna, situated on the banks of the Palala River, and with an unpolluted night sky. Delegates can roam freely and collect specimens across the secure, fenced 1,170-hectare property.

A Limpopo Province collecting permit will be available to all delegates.

Delegates that want to collect in other provinces, should contact the congress organizers for further detail.

FACILITIES AND OPTIONAL ACTIVITIES

- Free high-speed WiFi
- Swimming pool
- Bush walks
- Visit to rock art site
- Obstacle course (for those joined by their families, or who themselves feel young at heart)
- Game drives (one inclusive on registration; additional drives at additional cost)
- Hands-on outreach activities at a rural school (additional cost)

AFRAS

The AFRAS Colloquiums are tri-annual meetings of local and international arachnologists who research African arachnids. We strongly encourage participation by students and fellow arachnologists in Africa. AFRAS is a non-profit organization. Membership is free.

Further details on the 15th AFRAS colloquium will be updated on the colloquium website (<https://afras2027.carlamani.com/>). If the website does not open, refresh the page or open in different browser such as Chrome. The website can also be reached via the AFRAS website at <http://afras.ufs.ac.za>.

Or contact Tharina at the following details:

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We are looking forward to seeing you here!

Tharina Bird (AFRAS Chair) and organizing committee.